

where R = ratio of price/kg of nutrient to price/kg grain.

Fertilizer adjustment equations for economic yield, worked out for nitrogen

and phosphorus, obeyed the law of diminishing returns. The recommended fertilizer doses are useful because they are not only based on soil test values but

also take into account the relative cost of fertilizer nutrients and price of the crop. ■

Response of Basmati 370 to azolla application

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The water fern azolla, with its nitrogen-fixing *Anabaena* endosymbiont, has certain limitations when used as a biological source of nitrogen in rice cultivation. Its sensitivity to high light intensity and temperature becomes a major constraint to large-scale use in northern and some parts of eastern India. This study deals with the effect of dried azolla on nitrogen uptake and yield of Basmati 370.

Azolla fortified with 150 g superphosphate was grown during the September-October season in polythene-lined, shallow, 2-m² ponds. Periodic harvests (15-day intervals) were sundried and

Yield and nitrogen uptake by Basmati 370, northern India, 1979 wet season.^a

Treatment ^b	Yield (g/pot)		N uptake (mg/pot)
	Grain	Straw	
Control	3.58	4.01	53.4
Azolla	5.6	5.0	76.4
60 kg N	14.4	12.0	193.9
60 kg N + azolla	19.3	16.6	259.4
80 kg N	19.3	16.6	267.7
80 kg N + azolla	27.9	21.8	374.3
100 kg N	28.0	22.1	259.9
100 kg N + azolla	32.9	28.2	453.7
C.D. 5%	1.25	1.65	

^aValues are mean of 3 replications. ^bAzolla rate was 1 t/ha.

stored. In randomized pot culture experiments during the 1979 wet season, each pot contained 14 kg soil, 4 rice seedlings, and phosphorus and potassium at the rate of 50 kg/ha. Three levels of urea (60, 80, and 100 kg N/ha) were applied as a basal dose with and without dried azolla at 1 t/ha).

Crop yield was a function of fertilizer nitrogen input, showing a progressive

increase from 60 N to 100 N (see table). Grain and straw yields increased significantly when nitrogen was supplemented by dry azolla. At every nitrogen level, the effect of azolla supplementation was equal to that of the next higher nitrogen level without azolla. The azolla was the equivalent of 20 kg N/ha. Nitrogen uptake also showed significant increases with dried azolla application. ■

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